

REVIEWS

THE TRUE COUNTRY MEETS AMERICA MIDNIGHT OIL IN THE USA

Rochester N.Y. - It's midnight at the Renaissance Club and the roadies have just completed packing the equipment. Those of us with the right connections are ushered into the hospitality area, a harshly lit room with all the charm of a railway urinal. The band, however, has decided not to party and retired to the bar at their motel. Although invited to join them, us backstage devotees feel that perhaps the band wants to wind down alone. After all we have had our monies worth; *Midnight Oil* gave us their all in a high-charged performance that Australians recognize as the hallmark of a band that paid its dues on the pub rock circuit. It was difficult at times to remember that this was Rochester, New York. Up on the stage were the symbols of Australia: a kangaroo, a dingo and Peter Garrett. The audience, hot and sweaty, cheered. For a moment it could have been the Trade Union Club but the lack of decent beer forced the reality of America back upon a suddenly homesick Australian.

Earlier I had pondered what *Midnight Oil*, the quintessential Australian political band, has to say to an American audience in the twilight days of the Reagan regime. Peter Garrett answered the question at a press conference. *Midnight Oil* are a band, not a political party, and it is their music that appeals to Americans, and no doubt Australians, first and foremost. If, as Garrett and drummer Rob Hirst observed, America is the land of consumption gone mad, it is also the home of the dream of democracy.

In response to a question about the positive aspects of America Garrett expressed views that might shock some die hard anti-American Australians. Americans enjoy a society more receptive than Australia to different ideas. The written constitution guarantees certain rights that create a different political ideal; Americans take seriously the idea of community control of schools and the law, things Australians leave to the state. And finally, the American press is more varied and open than in Australia, especially since the closure of the *National Times* (*Times on Sunday*).

Do not despair, the *Oils* have not gone soft on America, Hirst and Garrett lambasted the destruction of the environment carried out in the name of development and progress. They realize, however, that there are many Americas just as there are many Australias.

At the Renaissance Club the band plays "Dead Heart". As Garrett sings, "we carry in our heart the true country and we will not be broken", he evokes images of Australia, my Australia, his Australia, Black Australia. Different images of Australia that retain their value for us above and beyond the hubris of the Bicentennial and the fitting mockery of the Sirius unfurling the Coke flag. The "true country" is something we all have an image of. For many young Australians it is *Midnight Oil* that best expresses what it means to be an Australian. In this way Garrett is not boasting when he says that the band (and its fans) were the defacto opposition in Australia at one stage.

In America a notion of the "true country" is perhaps more contested than in Australia. As a band *Midnight Oil* brings an Australian image of America to Americans. If there is to be a renaissance in American political thought and direction the young Republicans dancing to "Beds are Burning" at the Renaissance Club are among those who will have to bring it about. Did Bob Hawke influence as many American minds, as *Midnight Oil*, on his trip to Washington in June? Perhaps not.

IAN GORDON
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HUNTERS & COLLECTORS /PAUL KELLY Selina's; Sat 23rd July

Having a group of friends whose musical preferences consist of grunge, grunge and more grunge can have its drawbacks. Take last Saturday night for example. Thanking my lucky stars that neither Lubricated Goat nor Thug were playing anywhere (bands whose appeal lasts about as long as it takes to light the first cigarette of the night), my hopes of seeing a straight rock 'n' roll band were dashed by a general consensus to go and see The Debrovniks and then Toys went Berserk. Although both are several cuts above the depths reached by The Goat neither could satisfy my craving for a fix of mainstream oz rock.

Resolving to be independent, I set off for Selina's by myself, only to be flagged down on the corner of City Rd/Cleveland St by a considerate boyfriend who had at the last minute opted out of the grunge alternative.

Walking in at 10.30 p.m. Paul Kelly and his Coloured Girls (who are actually all Caucasian males) were already swinging. And the sounds they were making were just what the Dr ordered: good beefy rock 'n' roll with that typical flavour of sensitivity that Paul Kelly manages to blend into all his work. Especially impressive were the perfect harmonies provided by the drummer, and the outstanding harmonica/percussion/saxophone work emanating from the guest star from Harem Scarem. All in all, a performance that lived up to what has come to be expected of these seasoned performers, as was shown by the enthusiastic cries for an encore which were, for some reason, denied.

Almost time for Hunnas and the excitement was growing in the crowd: every roadie who ventured on stage to make some technical adjustment was greeted with a cheer which soon died when it became obvious that they were not a member of "the band". Eventually though the Hunnas appeared and it was straight into the brassy power pop that the metamorphosed Hunnas are known and loved for. Although I can't remember exactly the songs played (spot the journals at Selina's with pen and paper in hand!)

It suffices to say that there was a good mixture of old and new, as well as a preview of the new single "Inside a Fireball" was in my opinion the climax of the set, but I can't help feeling that a rendition of "Throw your arms around me" (which didn't feature at all as a final encore would have brought the fever of the evening to an even higher pitch than that reached during "Fireball"). Despite the professionalism and punch of the band (marred only by Mark Seymour's continual battle with a microphone that had a mind of its own) I couldn't get out of my mind an observation made by one of my friends who had refused to come with me: "Mark Seymour is a real jerk" he had said. I had dismissed this as a criticism that this particular friend would level at any band/singer who played music rather than feedback, but alas, the comment contained grains of truth. Hasn't somebody told Mr Seymour that playing up to a teen-idol image does not do much for street-credibility? Doesn't he know that squeezing the hands of girls in the front row went out with Daryl Braithwaite? But perhaps I am just falling into the standard trap of lamenting the changes that inevitably follow when a band becomes successful, and if so I apologise. In the end, it must be said that the concert was thoroughly enjoyable, but that next week it's back to the Hopetoun or Max's at Petersham for something with a little more communication between audience and band.

ANNE WHITEHEAD

